

"GEOGRAFIYANÍŇ AKTUAL MASHQALALARI HÁM RAWAJLANÍW PERSPEKTIVALARI"

atındađı respublikalıq ilimiy-ámeliy konferenciya

EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN, FACTORS AFFECTING IT, AND PERSPECTIVE OPPORTUNITIES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF BERUNIY DISTRICT)

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Abstract. *This article provides data on the number and location of industrial enterprises in the regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The volume of industrial products produced by industrial enterprises is indicated by territory. The prospects for further placement of industrial enterprises in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan by region were considered.*

Key words: *Republic of Karakalpakstan, Nukus, Beruni, industry, enterprise, district, product.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi hududlaridagi sanoat korxonalarining soni, joylashuvi haqida ma'lumotlar berib o'tilgan. Sanoat korxonolari tomonidan tayyorlangan sanoat mahsulotlari hajmi hududlar kesimida ko'rsatilib o'tilgan. Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi hududida sanoat korxonalarini kelajakda hududlar bo'yicha joylashtirish istiqbollari haqida fikr yuritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi, Nukus, Beruniy, sanoat, korxonona, tuman, mahsulot.*

The Strategy of Actions for the Socio-Economic Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan attaches great importance to the issues of accelerating the development of productive forces, particularly in the industrial sector, and rational territorial organisation. In the processes of modernisation and diversification of the economy, the core of the country's economic strategy is to increase the efficiency of industrial production and its quality indicators¹.

As of January 2024, industrial enterprises located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan produced industrial products worth 18,803.1 billion soums (Table 1). The leaders in industrial production volume in the republic are the city of Nukus, as

¹ Egamberdiyeva U.T. Sanoat geografiyasi: darslik / Egamberdiyeva U.T., -Toshkent: «Donishmand ziyosi», 2020. - 232 b.

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well as the Takhiatash and Kungirat districts. As of January 1, 2024, 3,666 industrial enterprises continue to operate in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In terms of regions, the leaders are Nukus city - 661, Amudarya district - 375, Ellikkal'a district - 346, Turtkul district - 338, Beruni district - 290, and Kungirat district - 280 (Table 1).

Table 1

Volume of industrial products produced by regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

№	Region	Number of industrial enterprises	Volume of industrial products (in billion Uzbek soums)	Average volume per industrial enterprise (in billion Uzbek soums)
1	Nukus City	661	8533,3	12,9
2	Amudarya District	375	944,2	2,5
3	Ellikkal'a District	346	586,6	1,7
4	Turtkul District	338	840,0	2,5
5	Beruni District	290	691,4	2,4
6	Kungrad District	280	1259,8	4,5
7	Khojayli District	207	449,4	2,2
8	Karauzak District	167	657,8	3,9
9	Chimbay District	159	417,6	2,6
10	Muynak District	148	307,0	2,1
11	Takhiatash District	139	2282,5	16,4
12	Kegeyli District	120	378,4	3,2
13	Takhtakupir District	118	329,0	2,8
14	Nukus District	101	393,0	3,9
15	Qonlikul District	82	414,9	5,1
16	Shumanay District	75	278,4	3,7
17	Bozataw District	60	39,8	0,7
Total		3666	18803,1	

Note: the values are shown in Uzbek soums

Almost 1/3 or 62.3 per cent of the industrial enterprises in the Republic of Karakalpakstan are located in these regions. On the contrary, 82 industrial enterprises operate in Qonlikul district, 75 in Shumanay district, and 60 in Bozatov district. In total, these districts have 217 or 5.8 per cent of the industrial enterprises in the

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Republic (Diagram 1). The districts with the largest number of industrial enterprises are Amudaryo, Ellikkal'a, Turtkul', while the lowest indicator is in Bozatov, Shumanay, and Qonlikul districts. This is because Amudaryo, Ellikkal'a, Tortkul', and Beruniy districts are located adjacent to the Amu Darya River and the fact that the population has been living in these districts for a long time. This can be explained by the remote and marginal location of the Qonlikul, Shumanay, and Bozatov districts, their small population, and the incomplete development of the necessary infrastructure for the development of industry.

Figure 1. Share of industrial enterprises of Karakalpakstan

Along with the laws of the location of productive forces, the principles of their location are also of great importance. In a market economy, the principles of the location of production can be understood as a kind of scientific regulation of state economic policy. When the principle of bringing production closer to sources of energy, raw materials, fuel and consumption regions is implemented, the problems

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associated with long-distance freight transportation and reducing costs in the production process are solved. This, in turn, leads to an increase in economic efficiency².

In recent years, the essential infrastructure for industrial enterprises has been gradually developing in the regions surrounding Nukus. This offers an opportunity to establish large and small industrial enterprises in other parts of the republic. Notably, foreign and local entrepreneurs are mainly setting up these industries in regions adjacent to Nukus, such as Amudarya, Beruniy, Ellikkal'a, and Kungirat. The geographical position of Beruniy district holds particular significance for the location of future industrial enterprises in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. For instance, Beruniy is 25.3 km from Bo'ston, the centre of Ellikkal'a district; 28.5 km from Turtkul, the centre of Torkul district; and 22.7 km from Urgench, the capital of Khorezm region. The proximity of these cities facilitates the marketing of industrial products produced by these enterprises within the domestic market.

Beruniy district has the most necessary qualified workforce and sufficient infrastructure to establish modern industrial enterprises. This can also help ensure employment in the regions adjacent to the district. According to the analysis of the economically active population in Beruniy district and adjacent regions, Beruniy district has 81.4 thousand people, Ellikkal'a district has 70.2 thousand people, Turtkul district has 81.5 thousand people, and Urgench city has 91.0 thousand people, or the total number of economically active population in the regions is 324.1 thousand people.

Also, the Beruniy district has a developed transport system for transporting industrial products. For example, the A-380 highway "Guzor-Bukhara-Nukus-Beyneu" passes through the district, a railway capable of carrying out international transportation, and the proximity of the Urgench International Airport in the city of Urgench (22.2 km from the city of Beruniy) determine the transport potential of the district.

In conclusion, the geographical location and transport infrastructure of the Beruniy district make it a favourable area for the operation of modern industrial enterprises. The qualified workforce in the district, short distances to nearby cities, and a developed transport system ensure the effective sale of industrial products in the domestic market and strengthen regional economic integration. The distances between the Beruniy district and the nearby cities of Ellikkal'a, Torkul'l, and Urgench

² <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ishlab-chiqarish-kuchlarini-joylashtirish-tamoyillari/viewer>

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are relatively small, which allows for the fast and efficient delivery of industrial products.

The high number of economically active population (totalling 324.1 thousand people) is a necessary factor for meeting the demand for qualified labour and the development of industrial enterprises. The presence of the A-380 highway, the international railway, and the Urgench airport increases transport capacity and expands access to domestic and international markets. These conditions make the Beruni district an important strategic area for industrial development and economic integration. Thus, the Beruniy district, with its convenient location, developed transport infrastructure, and economic potential in nearby regions, will be the basis for the success of industrial enterprises and regional economic growth.

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